

Crowd-sourced data for traffic flow estimate for environmental pollution decision tools

PROJECT STAGES TOWARDS NOISE DYNAMIC MAPS

Traffic model is developed together with the mapping in Pisa, where the whole system is calibrated and parameters established.

All the parameters are set up within the two first stages and then applied in Brindisi, where replication will be carried out.

The network → **The traffic** → **The noise**

A selection of roads where Google travel times are available is performed (manually). Road classes of roads are taken from Open Street Map with corresponding origin-destination coordinates for each direction.

A pipeline is established in Python to call API services, obtain travel times, establish flows based on transportation equation and parameters obtained at calibration stage.

Sound power of roads is established according to CNOSSOS-EU and calculation at receivers is achieved by sum with abatement matrix, which is calculated only once for the given area.

A noise map at receivers potentially every 5 minutes

LOOK to DYNAMIC MAP IN THE TEST AREA

SPEED

The developed pipeline is based on a simple transportation equation; thus, the results of each road flow are independent and based on travel time from API services. The whole pipeline from the call to the sound at receivers can be computed in **few seconds**.

In fact, all the **computation load relies with abatement matrix** which is computed only once (before the calls). The time needed for abatement matrix obviously depends on standard mapping parameters such as terrain and obstacles, number of roads, number of receivers, maximum research radius (how far we look for sources from receivers).

TRAFFIC ACCURACY

Flows are derived from travel times, but API provides a traffic aware travel time when a sufficient flow occurs, otherwise average values are returned without labeling of such cases. Thus, **estimates are inaccurate for low traffic**.

Estimates also fails when the network has no continuous traffic flows, since we applied simple transportation equation (BPR function).

Traffic flows differences between estimates and measurements are represented in terms of expected difference in noise, comparing log of flows ratio.

NOISE LEVELS ACCURACY

Noise levels are measured with 5 monitoring stations for a full week. Data are acquired for calibration in a secondary, tertiary and a residential road together with traffic flows. For the validation, two more roads are selected for noise measurements that reveals as secondary and secondary dual lane.

Average differences increases during evening and night periods and for low traffic roads, e.g. residential average difference during night is more than 10 dB(A).

Phase	Calibration			Validation	
	secondary	tertiary	residential	secondary	secondary dual lane
MEAN [dB(A)]	0.0	-1.9	-4.9	-0.2	-1.1
STD [dB(A)]	4.0	6.5	8.5	4.5	3.7

Conclusions

	Helpful	Harmful
Internal	STRENGTHS Data are widespread so the approach allow large scale remotely applicability; It offers dynamic narrow scale.	WEAKNESSES The approach fails in case of road not covered by the API service or low traffic; It needs some modal local data.
External	OPPORTUNITIES Data could feed micro-simulations models of traffic and feed ITS.	THREATS Costs of data are not negligible for large scale studies.

Perspectives

To feed Digital Twin with noise exposure data, complaints, mobility data and integrate other results such as air pollutants exposure.

To provide policy makers with a tool for planning and acting purposes such as a digital twin integrated with traffic models and ITS systems able to mitigate noise pollution.

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